

HERBALISTS AND MENTAL HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR AMONG THE IBIBIO PEOPLE OF SOUTHERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Mental health issue generates great concern among the Ibibio people of South-South Nigeria due to their culturally adopted belief that “Abud isi imummo idad, ase amumm ayeneka ida” (a mad man is not ashamed of his madness, but his relatives are caught with shame). This research work examined the level and reasons of patronage of herbalists for Mental Illness by the Ibibio People of Akwa Ibom State in Southern Nigeria. The researchers made use of explanatory model, holistic model and health belief model (HBM) as theoretical frameworks for the study. Ibibio speaking local government areas were purposively selected, and clustered into the 3 existing senatorial districts. Study participants were randomly selected from 16 Ibibio clans, from randomly selected Ibibio speaking local government areas. Study respondents were engaged in interviews and their socio demographic data collected were presented. Findings of the study were analyzed qualitatively in thematic analysis with excerpts from the study participants. Findings of the study revealed that Ibibio people have great belief that mental illness is spiritually influenced and due to high preference of herbs, the Ibibio people grow the attitude of patronizing herbalists for treatment of mental illness; priority is given to treatment with spiritual powers which faith healers and traditional herbalists are the most patronized in terms of mental health services. It was concluded that, out of fear of being stigmatized; Ibibio people chose not to go to psychiatric hospitals for treatments to avoid the cultural implication of stigmatization which also contribute to the high dependency on faith healing and herbal treatments. The researcher among others recommended that the Ibibio people should be educated on mental health and illnesses in order to reduce the stigmatization and the belief in spiritual causes of mental illness among the people and throughout Akwa Ibom State.

Keywords: Mental illness, Herbs, Herbalists, and Ibibio People

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental health according to Stein (2013) could be seen as the successful performance of mental functions resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships, and the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity. The reverse is mental illness. Mental illness refers to a wide range of mental health disorders that affect the mood, thinking, behaviour and one's ability to function in social, work or family activities (APA, 2018). Mental health disorders constitute the major causes of disabilities worldwide, accounting for 37% of all healthy life years lost through disease (Jack-Idé, Uys and Middleton, 2013). It is also universal, affecting people of all countries and societies, regardless of age, gender and income. The prevalence of mental illness in the adult population at any given time is about 10% (Cuijpers and Stam 2003). Similarly, around 20% of all patients seen by primary health care providers have one or more mental health disorders.

Mohr (2003) quoted by America Psychiatric Association (APA) that mental illness is considered a clinical significant behavioural or psychological syndrome experienced by a person and marked by distress, disability or the risk of suffering disability or loss of freedom. It could be marked by alterations in thinking, mood or behaviour that cause distress, impaired ability to function or both. According to *Stein, Phillips, Bolton, Fulford, Sadler, and Kendler, (2010)*, a mental disorder is a psychological syndrome or pattern which is associated with distress (e.g. via a painful symptom), disability (impairment in one or more important areas of functioning), increased risk of death, or causes a significant loss of autonomy; however it excludes normal responses such as grief from loss of a loved one, and also excludes deviant behaviour for political, religious, or societal reasons not arising from a dysfunction in the individual. Mental Health Association in Forsyth County (2009) defines mental illness as a disease of the brain that causes mild to severe disturbances in thought and/or behaviour, resulting in an inability to cope with life's ordinary demands and routines. There are more than 200 classified forms of mental illness (Mental Health Association, 2009). Some of the more common disorders are: clinical depression, bipolar disorder, dementia, schizophrenia and anxiety disorders. Mental illness therefore involves expression of distress, an inability to be independent as well as alteration of mood, behaviour or thought due to a malfunctioning of a certain human organ responsible for these or any of these (Mental Health Association, 2009).

Mental illness is a disabling, chronic condition that poses numerous challenges in its management and its risk factors for other health problems (Kabir, *et al.*, 2004). It bestows significant costs to the patient in terms of personal suffering, to the families as a result of the shift of burden of care and life-time loss of productivity, and on the society at large. It is reported that mental and behavioural disorders are common, affecting more than 25% of all people at some time (Kabir, *et al.*, 2004). The prevalence of mental illness or disorder in some communities around the world

makes availability of mental health care service a necessity. According to Azeem (2014), there is the need for community-based services to be delivered in the primary care setting to provide accessible and humane mental health care. In low-income and middle-income countries, support for primary care services to enable them to identify and treat people with mental disorders, with training, assistance, and supervision by available specialist mental health staff is the best way to extend mental health care to the population (Desjarlais, Eisenberg, Good, and Kleinman, 1995).

Societies across the world have different explanatory perspectives as it relates to the nature, causes and interventions for mental health problems (Ahmed, San and Nazar, 2015). These perspectives are as a result of certain aspects of the cultural practices of the society, which is entrenched in the way the people think, reason, act, and speak (Ahmed, *et al.*, 2015). The role of the community in the prevention and care of the mentally handicapped has now been widely acknowledged and is regarded as the most appropriate basis for the development of mental health programmes (Kabir *et al.*, 2004). Several studies have shown that knowledge of public attitude to mental illness and its treatment are vitally important prerequisite to the realization of successful community-based programmes. The norms, beliefs and customs within the individual's cultural environment, play a significant role in the recognition, care and management of mental disorder (Kabir *et al.*, 2004).

The health seeking behaviour of a community determines how health services are used and in turn the health outcomes of populations (Shaikh and Hatcher, 2005). Up to about 70% to 80% of the population of mentally ill belong to rural areas and first visit religious places and consult with the indigenous practitioner for their treatment (Subhudi, 2015). Factors that determine health seeking behaviour may be physical, socio-economic, cultural or political. Indeed, the utilisation of a health care system may depend on educational levels, economic factors, cultural beliefs and practices. Other factors include environmental conditions, socio-demographic factors, and knowledge about the facilities, gender issues, political environment, and the health care system itself (Ogunlesi, and Olanrewaju, 2010).

Research on health seeking behaviour during mental illness has been done in several areas of the world though not much has been done in the South Southern region of Nigeria. Evidences abound of how the mentally ill and their relatives approach the challenge of mental illness in their bid to seek cure or relief. According Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009), it is widely acknowledged that sub-Saharan Africa is deficient in providing prompt and effective professional mental health services, which are needed to avoid chronic illness and the establishment of irreversible squealed.

Equally, Burns and Tomita (2015) observed that there is good evidence for a considerable mental health treatment gap in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) due to a lack of adequate infrastructure, human resources and

treatment options. This is nowhere more apparent than on the African continent, where data from the World Health Organization's Atlas Project on mental health shows widespread, systematic and long-term neglect of resources for mental health care in low income and middle-income countries (Burns and Tomita, 2015).

Additionally, Jimenez, Bartels, Cardenas, Daliwal, and Alegría (2012) posit that beliefs concerning the causes of mental illness may help explain why there are significant disparities in the rates of formal mental health service use. Most cultures especially in Africa have been found to adopt the complementary and traditional medical practices to solve the problems of mental ill health. According to Sorsdahl, Stein, Grimsrud, Seedat, Flisher, Williams, and Myer, (2009), several studies have shown that alternative practitioners play an important role in addressing mental health care needs in South Africa by offering culturally appropriate treatment. In many traditional African belief systems, mental health problems are perceived as due to ancestors or by bewitchment and traditional healers and religious advisors are viewed as having expertise in these areas (Nattrass, 2005; Mbanga, Niehaus and Mzamo, 2002).

In India, the mental health resources are very low compared with high-income countries. According to a recent estimate, the country has just 0.25 psychiatric beds per 10,000 population, 0.2 psychiatrists, 0.03 clinical psychologists, 0.05 psychiatric nurses, and 0.03 social workers per 100,000 of the population (Alegría, Bijl, Lin, Walters, and Kessler, 2000). The facilities for psychiatric treatment are generally available in general hospital psychiatric units, mental hospitals, and office-based practice. Besides these, the patients, depending on the availability and accessibility, may consult a non-psychiatric physician, general practitioner, lay counselor, local religious leaders, or traditional faith healer (Andrews, Issakidis, and Carter, 2001).

On the perceived efficacy of the alternative and traditional mental health care which may have sustained their belief and patronage in low – income countries, researchers have discovered relative levels of efficacy. Abbo (2011), reviewed profiles and outcome of traditional healing practices for severe mental illnesses in two districts of Eastern Uganda and observed that for a cohort of patients with severe mental illness attending traditional healers there was a general trend for symptom scales to show a reduction at the 3- and 6-month follow-ups. However, in terms of patients' cutoff points for diagnosis, the general improvement at 3 months was greatest in patients with mania (54.0percent), less so with psychotic depression (42.0percent), and least with schizophrenia (14.8percent). At 6 months, the percentage of patients who showed an improvement was as follows: mania (58.3percent), psychotic depression (46.4percent), and schizophrenia (30.7percent) (Abbo, 2011).

However, Burns and Tomita (2015), in a study traditional and religious healers in the pathway to care for people with mental disorders in Africa: a systematic review and

meta-analysis, noted that in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), a considerable proportion of individuals seeking care for mental disorders consult traditional and religious healers in their pathway to mental health care. Such early involvement of healers may result in delays in the care pathway; a potential barrier to early identification and intervention. This however portrays a lack of effective cure of the mental illness by the traditional and religious healers which may result in the patient and relatives seeking other means, usually orthodox, of treatment for the ailment (Burns and Tomita, 2015).

Burns and Tomita further maintained that traditional and religious healers have been identified as herbalists, diviners and faith healers in this study, the level of patronage of each in Nigeria and other African countries will paint a clearer picture of health seeking behaviour for the mentally ill in these areas thus providing the review upon which this study is premised. Sorsdahl *et al.*, (2009) in their study traditional healers in the treatment of common mental disorders in South Africa, observed that of the participants who sought treatment (regardless of whether they met lifetime DSM-IV criteria for a disorder or not), 21percent were treated by Western practitioners, 13percent were treated by alternative practitioners, and 7percent by a combination of both Western, and alternative practitioners. Of the subjects who sought treatment from alternative medicine, 6percent sought treatment from a traditional healer, 7percent of the sample sought treatment from a spiritual or religious advisor, and 2percent by another type of healer. However, while 14percent of study participants sought treatment from a Western practitioner exclusively, only 2percent sought treatment from a traditional healer exclusively (Sorsdahl *et al.*, 2009).

Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) in a study; preferred treatment for mental illness among Southwestern Nigerians showed that 844 (41percent) study participants indicated spiritual healers as their preferred treatment option, whereas 634 (30percent) indicated traditional healers and 600 (29percent) indicated Western medicine. They also found that the factors that were independently associated with preference for spiritual or traditional healers included being female, having a lower level of education, having never cared for a person with mental illness, and endorsement of supernatural causal beliefs. Further analysis of the data by Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) showed that the bulk of the gender difference was in the spiritual healers' option alone, with no gender difference in the option of traditional healers.

In India, a middle income countries outside Africa, Mishra, Nappal, Chadda and Sood (2011), observe that nearly one third of the patients consulted a traditional faith healer or an alternative medicine practitioner at some point of course of their illness. Similarly, more than 80percent of the patients also consulted a non-psychiatric physician at some time for their mental health problem. However, a recent study from

a psychiatric hospital in the state of Madhya Pradesh (Central India) found faith healers as the first contact of help in 68% of the total sample. Most of the patients in these studies suffered from psychotic disorders of different types.

In the first two studies, having been conducted in the cities of Delhi and Bangalore, majority of the patients were from urban background, whereas in the third study, nearly 70percent of the sample was from a rural background. Another reason for a high percentage of patients going to faith healers as the first contact in the study could be that number of psychiatrists in the state of Madhya Pradesh is much lower compared with the places of other studies.

Effiong and Albert (2016) in their study; Pathways to Psychiatric Care among Patients with Schizophrenia in Nigeria, it was found that majority of participants (76.8percent) patronized non-orthodox treatment facility as their first treatment option in help seeking for mental disorders. This, the study showed, comprises (65.7percent) of those who patronized religious healers as their first contact and (11.1percent) of participants who visited traditional healers for their first treatment attention. The study also showed that 41.7percent visited a second religious treatment centre and 36.8percent visited a third before attention in a tertiary psychiatric facility.

The Ibibio is the major tribe in Akwa Ibom State with a population of about 3.1 million which is about 60% of the state's population, going by the fact that the tribe forms about 16 of the 36 Local Government Areas of the state (Essien, 1990). The Ibibio is one of the oldest ethnic groups in Nigeria with its customs, culture, ethics and mores. These are determined by the belief system of the Ibibio people who are known for their distinct cultural belief on spirit beings and ancestors who live in the afterlife just like they in life (Essien, 1990). The belief also portrays the spirit being as having powers to influence human activities including health, economy, favour etc (Essien, 1990). Health challenges are usually associated with offences against the deities, gods and/or ancestors. This makes the appeasement of the gods or deities a necessity in health management in the history of Ibibio. The nature of the ailment is related to symptoms assumed or heard of (Essien, 1990). Divinity is usually resorted to in the cause of diagnosis. All these depend on the cultural background of the Ibibio. Almost everything in Ibibio is woven around religion. From childbirth, fertility, health, fortune and even influence in the society is assumed to be controlled in the spiritual realm (Oreva 2018).

Mental illness is not alien to Ibibio culture and the Ibibio have attempted to demystify the problem so that permanent solution can be given to this illness which is assumed to affect the family members more than the mentally ill because Ibibio adage says "*Obut isi mummo Idat ase omum eyeneka Idat*" (The shame of madness does not bother the mad person, but members of his/her family). Various strategies have been adopted by different families to care, treat and manage the mentally ill with the desire of returning them to normalcy.

With the low level of orthodox mental healthcare delivery in Nigeria, the mentally ill seek other alternatives to solving their problems. Gureje and Lasebikan (2006) observed that the service gap left by orthodox mental health practice in Nigeria is filled by traditional, spiritual, faith healing and complementary medicine, the use of which is widespread in most communities, as lay perception of mental disorders are still rooted in super-natural belief systems especially among the Ibibio people, and therefore considered untreatable with western medicine. This background provides the gap as in investigating the level and reasons for patronage of herbalists as a preferred mental health care alternative among the Ibibio people which this research work sought to fill.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Mental Health Seeking Behaviour Model (MHSBM)

Source: Esen (2019).

The major components of MHSBM include;

- i) **Family of the patients:** In Ibibio land, it is well stated and culturally rooted that; “*Abud isi mummo idad, ase amum ubon idad.*” This is translated as; “*shame or disgrace of madness always accorded the family of the mad man, NOT the mad man himself.*” The family of the mentally ill person is the one who bear the burden of seeking treatment and healing for the said patient (their son/daughter).
- ii) **Collective Perceived Threat:** This refers to the consequences and cost (shame, disgrace, losses through violent behavior of the patients, etc.), which the family stands to suffer if the said patient (their son/daughter) is not treated and restore to normal health or healed on time.
- iii) **Collective Belief:** This refers to the agreement of the family on a given choice of treatment base on the likely perceive benefits of the choice. This is also base

on the level of availability of resources which the family will depend upon throughout the process of treating the said patient (their son/daughter).

iv) **Collective Behaviour:** This refers to the response of the family toward the treatment/healing of the said patient (their son/daughter). This is based on the likely benefits which the family perceives in available treatment options, which is also based on the availability of resources which will enhance patronage of such available treatment option by the family.

v) **Cue to Action:** This refers to readiness to take action toward the treatment of the said patient (their son/daughter).

3. METHODOLOGY

An ethnographic research design was adopted with a multi-stage type of data collection approach. The study area was Akwa Ibom state. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria, created on the 23rd of September 1987, with Uyo as its capital. Akwa Ibom is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with a population of over five million people (NPC, 2006). The study was conducted among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. The Ibibio people are a coastal people in southern Nigeria (Cole and Derk, 2012). They are mostly found in Akwa Ibom. They are related to the Anaang, Igbo and Efik peoples. The Annang, Efik, and Oron share personal names, culture, and traditions with the Ibibio, and speak closely related varieties of Ibibio-Efik which are more or less mutually intelligible (Okon, 1984). Masks are a primary aspect of art made by the Ibibio.

The researchers adopted a big-net approach (Fatterman, 2010) to gather information from the study participants. Participant observation, in-depth interview (II), key informant interview (KII), and focus group discussions (FGDs) were used by the researchers to obtain primary data. Secondary data were collected through published materials and internet sources.

4. FINDINGS

4.1 *High preference to herbs*

Emergence from discussions and interviews revealed that Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State have high regards for herbs and roots medicine. This becomes a factor for the high level of patronage in mental health treatment. Gathered information from discussions and interviews showed that, the people of Ibibio patronize traditional herbalists for mental illness treatment. Many of them considered traditional herbalists' treatment as the first option when it comes to mental illness. One of the study participants aged 71 years in his responses said;

In this village, madness is a serious illness that nobody wants to joke with. If anybody suffers this kind of illness that first thing to do is to send that person to those who can handle it. This is because madness is controlled by beings we cannot see, therefore there are people with the divine gift which can use herbs to control those beings and get the person free from the illness (Anthony 71, interviewed on 24/8/2019).

A key informant in his explanations said;

When Late Etim Udoeyen was alive, one thing I realized was that people will bring their relatives who are just getting mad to him to cure. Why I say they were just getting mad was that you will differentiate them from those who have been taken to other places before based on the way they look new, decent, clean, and fresh. Sometimes when we looked at them from a distance we will begin to cry for them (Ekwere 40, interview conducted on 24/8/2019).

4.2 Dependency on herbs

Traditional herbalist practice within Ibibio land is part of the culture of other people over the generations. According to the majority of the study participants, the people used to live solely on natural herbs and roots for treatment of illness before the arrival of the colonial masters with the orthodox drugs which has gradually overtook the herbs and roots in the market place. Gathered information showed that many Ibibio people still depend on herbs and roots for treatment of diseases for what they may consider to be either physical or spiritual ailment. One of the study participant aged 46 years in her narratives said;

We were born into the use of herbs and roots in our family, and not only our family but every family in this community. Herbs and roots are still in use till today and a lot of them are far better in treating some ailments than the white-man drugs. I am still using it till today. Though we all used these roots and herbs, there are people with special gifts to know more of the herbs and roots than all of us. These people like the children of Akpan-Adia-Akpa, who inherited from their father, who also inherited from his own father, are still using these herbs and roots to cure madness today. People used to bring mad people to them and they treat very well (Mandu 46, interviewed on 24/8/2019).

4.3 Cultural belief in herbs

Emerging from discussion is the fact that there is a strong belief in herbal medicine among a good population of the Ibibio people. The majority of the study participants agreed that there exist a high level of belief among the Ibibio people in herbal medicine which has influenced their health seeking behaviour over the generations. This has become a great factor in mental health seeking behaviour.

Herbal medicine is still at a good competitive level with the orthodox medicine especially in the rural areas of the Ibibio land. People showed great belief in the efficacy of the herbal treatment especially when the traditional herbalist combines his practice with the spiritual practice of divination. One of the study participants aged 52 years, in his narrative said;

This village used to come to my grandfather for any help at all. There was no thief because if you still and the village come to my father, after his consultation he will tell the village who was responsible for the crime. The sick used to come to him for herbal

medicine to recover. Mad people were brought to him and he healed them. He passed it over to my father who passed it over to us. The people have continued to patronize us for herbal treatment even people from a far because they believe in traditional herbal medicine (Akpan-Adia-Akpa 52, interview conducted on 24/8/2019).

Traditional herbalists have been known for rendering treatment to mental illness among the people of Ibibio as in Ikot Ekpudo in Nsit Ubium Local Government Area. Study participants agreed that mentally ill patients have been coming from far and near. Ibibio people used to bring their relative from outside Akwa Ibom State for treatment to traditional herbalists. Mentally ill patients are said to have been brought from psychiatric hospital and prayer houses to be healed by traditional herbalists. One of the key informants in his narratives said;

My father used to heal people with herbs and roots. He used to heal mad people brought to him. When he died, I took over from him, and I have been healing mad people up till today. I have been receiving mad people from far and near, but none from this village because we have never had one. People used to bring their relatives who are mad from outside Akwa Ibom State like Port Harcourt and Abia State. Right from the days of my father, mad people were brought from hospital and we treat them and they recover very well. So, till today they still bring people from psychiatric hospital to me and I treatment. In fact, there was a time some students from psychiatric nursing school Calabar came and interviewed my late father. After few days, some people came to take him to Calabar I did not allow my father to go, I told him not to go. If they have any mad person, let them go and bring the person and they did (Nappy 53, interview conducted on 24/8/2019).

Another key informant from Ikot Edem Ekong in Ikot Eyo community in Nsit Ubim Local Government Area in his responses said;

We used to have one traditional herbalist who used to render treatment to mentally ill persons in this village though he is late. His name was called Etim Udoeyen. He has a son who has refused to take over from him therefore we do not have such person again in this community who can treat mental ill persons. People used to bring mad people from afar, some were brought from outside Akwa Ibom State, some were brought from psychiatric hospitals after receiving treatment there and it did not work for them, but to our surprise, we have not had any mentally ill person from this community (Okon 38, interviewed on 24/8/2019).

Mental illness among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State is treated in many ways. One of the treatment methods greatly valued by the people is the herbal treatment. Information gathered by the researcher revealed that the story of treating mentally ill patients in Ibibio land has spread across Akwa Ibom State and its neighbouring states. Patronage of traditional herbalists is not limited to the people of Ibibio.

4.4 Discussion of findings

Emerging from discussions and interviews on herbal treatment on mental illness among the Ibibio people, is the high level of trust and confidence exhibited by the people toward patronizing traditional herbalist. Further findings revealed that most traditional herbalists among the people of Ibibio are diviners, who combine both herbs and roots with spiritual ministrations to cure their patients. Controlling the patients was found not to be challenging task as some of the traditional herbalists have special herbs called “mkpakpa-efiang” which they use to tie the legs of the mentally ill patients, and the herbs will be stronger than chains. This implies that those patients who are violently strong to the extent that they will drag chains and cut them with a pull of their legs, could not cut tiny rob of herbs which a simple draw with ordinary hands will cut to pieces. The trust placed on traditional herbalists by the Ibibio people is also based on the fact that some people withdraw their mentally ill patients from hospitals to the traditional herbalists for treatments. Shaith and Hatcher (2005) give credence to these findings by stating that; the health seeking behaviour of a community determines how health services are used and in turn the health outcomes of populations. It was surprisingly discovered that despite the rising numbers of mentally ill persons found across Ibibio community, towns and cities, and the corresponding mental illness cure and care givers, mental illness, madness, lunatic, or insanity were not found in the community where there is a healer. This implies that in Ibibio land where there is madness or mental illness treatment and cure is, nobody in that community will be sick of or suffer such ailment, and this is to be a test of the efficacy of the healer known in that community.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to investigate the level and reasons behind patronage of herbalists for mental health by Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, southern Nigeria. Mental illness to the Ibibio people is spiritually controlled ailment which needs spiritual intervention for successful and effective treatment. High regards to herbs and the fact that many Ibibio people have depended on herbs even before the arrival of western medicines. Herbalist practice is one of the cultural practices of the Ibibio people. Out of fear of being stigmatized, the people will choose not to take their mentally ill patients to psychiatric hospital in order not to reveal the fact that they have madness or lunatic spirit in the family. Ibibio people are said to be afraid of getting married to or allow their children get married to members of family that has mentally ill patients. This is because of the fear that mental illness can be inherited or is in blood line. The majority of the people do not know or go to health care centres for mental health care because they do not have any knowledge of the availability of such care provisions. Therefore, in Ibibio land there is high level of patronage of herbalists for mental illness, and where there is madness or mental illness treatment and cure, nobody in that community is found to be sick of or suffer such ailment.

5.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made from the findings of this research:

1. Community sensitization on the availability of mental health care services at health care centres should be embarked upon in all Ibibio communities across the state.
2. More psychiatric hospitals should be built across the Ibibio speaking local government areas to match the rising number of mentally ill persons.
3. Government and non-government organizations should embark on proper education of the people on the causes of mental illness in order to replace or reduce the degree of belief that mental illness is a spiritual problem.
4. Proper education programmes should be conducted in order to reduce the level of stigmatization on mental illness among the Ibibio people.

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